

The metacognitive knowledge and regulation of selected grade 8 students of Rizal High School towards basic mathematics problem solving

Kristine Maryknoll T. Baracao, Roland James A. Baracao

Abstract

Metacognition is a critical component of mathematical problem solving. It is the ability to monitor and control our own thoughts, how we approach a problem and how we choose strategies to find a solution; in other words, it is the ability to think about thinking. In this regard, the researchers would like to explore this concept by assessing the Metacognitive Knowledge and Regulation of selected grade 8 students of Rizal High School and the relationship of these strands of metacognition to that of the students' performance in Mathematics and to know if it can discriminate high and low mathematical performance. A descriptive type of research was employed, specifically, descriptive survey and descriptive analysis. The researchers administered a 5-item basic mathematical word problem solving test consisting of a 7-item self-report inventory through google forms which were analyzed and interpreted using standardized scoring rubrics on each metacognitive domain. It was revealed that there is a significant relationship between the students' academic performance in Mathematics 8 and the aspects of metacognitive knowledge and planning as brought by the generated intercorrelation data. These findings indicate that enhancing the students' metacognitive knowledge and system of planning will greatly yield an increment on metacognitive abilities that may contribute to higher mathematics performance. In the Multiple Discriminant Analysis, the Wilk's Lambda of 0.74 implies high discriminative power in determining low and high performing grade 8 students. Prediction and evaluation were most predictive, hence most powerful in discriminating between low performing and high performing students with canonical discriminant coefficients of 0.46 and 0.63, respectively. Thus, focusing on the enhancement of the aspects of metacognition and the factors affecting it would be of great help to elevate the mathematical performance of students.

Keywords: Metacognition; Metacognitive knowledge; Metacognitive regulation; Academic achievement; Basic mathematics problem solving.

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Introduction

Mathematics has long played an important part in the education of the youth, the world's aspiring movers and shakers. Its diverse learning facets train today's learners for the future. It lays the foundations for the development of a more stable basis of mathematical knowledge, not only numerical but also analytical, stressing the broad sense of problem solving as an important method for understanding how to integrate mathematics in and beyond every established academic area. Yet it is observed perennially that the performance levels of grade 8 students in Rizal High School as determined by the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) through quarterly assessments in Mathematics from school year 2017-2018 to school year 2019-2020 shows that the MPS throughout the said school years range only from 33.50% to 54.30% which is still far from the target MPS of the DepEd Division of Pasig City which is 75%.

Investigating on the various factors possible, Mahmudi, et.al., (2018) asserted that some of the reasons why students experience difficulty learning and applying mathematics are low level of academic achievement which indicates that students who experience math failure often lack basic math skills/concepts that make learning higher mathematics possible; and metacognitive thinking deficits, which state that students who are not metacognitively adept will struggle to succeed in mathematics (Mowling & Sims, 2021).

However, the question is not often if a student understands a mathematical method or process; it is always whether they understand that they understand it and may therefore determine how to apply it. As a result, the principle of metacognition has been recognized as a critical component in the problem-solving process. It is said to be one of the most recent buzz terms in educational psychology. The length and abstract nature of the term make it seem overwhelming, but it is not as difficult to grasp as it seems. In spite of the fact that students awareness can lead them to a better performances, they still encounter difficulties in learning mathematics. Thus, there is a constant quest for better and higher-level learning methods to achieve the set cognitive goals in the said academic field of interest in all learning institutions, not just in the aforementioned school, to promote a more successful and productive imparting of information to the learners.

Contemporary Education viewpoint as cited by Jacobse and Harskamp (2012) explains that students become conscious of their own learning and ultimately regulate their learning process which leads to better success. Given this view, teachers should not only teach the material but the method of how to understand the content as well. When students are taught how to implement successful learning techniques, they partake in a mechanism known as metacognition. Metacognition is defined by Shimamura (2000) as cited by Trisnani and Winarso (2019) as the capacity to analyze and track one's own cognitive functions, such as one's thoughts and memories, so that a rational prediction can be made about potential success.

In general, metacognition is characterized as the ability to manage one's own thought processes in problem solving which involves continuous and conscious monitoring of the strategies and thinking processes used in carrying out a task, finding alternate ways in performing a task and testing the appropriateness and reasonableness of answers (Mowling & Sims, 2021). It is composed of two separate but connected strands; the metacognitive knowledge, which stresses knowing what you do. It pertains to the knowledge and beliefs which a learner has about his own mental resources in a situation, how well the learner thinks he is likely to perform the mathematical techniques and processes he should be able to use and his beliefs about the nature of mathematics itself; and the metacognitive regulation which is the ability to monitor and regulate learner's own thinking directed on the process of active monitoring and regulation of thinking which has something to do with "when, why and how" students explore, plan, monitor, regulate, and evaluate progress (Flavell, 1976; Brown, 1987).

Furthermore, metacognition, also known as "thinking about thinking," can be used to help students "remember how to learn" (Gunter & Raymond, 2020). This is accompanied by the use of metacognitive techniques that will aid in the achievement of any cognitive target in terms of learning in a specific topic. This include decisions that aid in identifying the mission on which one is actually working, checking on the actual progress of that job, evaluating the progress, and forecasting the results of that progress.

Students usually remember and apply procedures in a simple manner when addressing standard mathematics problems. However, if the dilemma is new, certain students can actually choose a method and stay on the same path for an extended period of time without going anywhere. Susilo and Retnawati (2018) referred to this action as chasing the wild mathematical goose. A different behavior is often observed: students leap from one rule to the next haphazardly in the hopes of finding the right answer, becoming irritated, disappointed, and eventually giving up. Teachers who experience both styles of failed activities may conclude that the students have not learned the skills and may need to re-teach them. This can work for some, but not for others who have the skills but are unable to determine which ones to use or to monitor their own skill usage. A more "metacognitive" instructor suggests that the students' difficulties may not be due to a lack of skills, but rather to a lack of self-regulation of the problem-solving process (Wong, 2015).

As a result, the idea of metacognition has gotten a lot of attention from mathematical teaching theorists and scholars for three major reasons. According to Mulyono and Hadiyanti (2018), the first reason for this is that metacognitive experience fosters positive thinkers and lifelong learners capable of dealing with new circumstances in a constantly developing environment. The second reason is that incorporating mathematical instruction develops learners who are capable of managing their own learning. Finally, a metacognitive knowledge base is needed for successful problem-solving learning instruction. When faced with a mathematical challenge, experts focus on more than just principles and procedures. They must also have access to metacognition, which is the information that professionals use in "planning, tracking, managing, sorting, and assessing cognitive tasks" (Lai et al., 2015). Problem solvers who possess this higher order reasoning ability will be confident in the effectiveness of any mathematical technique they employ.

These significantly reveal the existence of metacognition as a foundation for a more methodical deliberation that may aid teachers in strengthening foundations in the field of Mathematics, which is avowed to have direct effects on students' behaviors toward mathematical word problem solving, thus affecting their level of performance in the said mathematical field of study.

It is for these reasons and arguments that the researchers conceived of undertaking a study to assess the Metacognitive Knowledge and Metacognitive Regulation and the relationship of these strands of metacognition to that of the students' performance in Mathematics of randomly selected Grade 8 students of Rizal High School, Division of Pasig City. The researchers would like to explore the concept of metacognition in the grade 8 students' problem-solving performance to also assess if the students' metacognition can discriminate high and low performance in Mathematics 8 which could possibly lead to further research regarding strategies or techniques to be developed to help enhance the Mathematics performance of grade 8 students through metacognition.

This hopefully may serve as their primary tool to successfully understand and answer mathematical word problems that can be a ground to make appropriate suggestions on how to increase mathematical performance.

Research Questions

Generally, the study is an attempt to assess the selected Rizal High School Grade 8 students' metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive regulation of S.Y. 2020-2021 towards basic mathematical word-problem solving. Specifically, it intends to answer the following questions:

1. What is the academic performance of the respondents in Mathematics during the First and Second Quarters, SY 2020-2021?
2. What is the metacognitive knowledge of Grade 8 students of Rizal High School in Basic Mathematics in the following aspects:
 - 2.1. Declarative knowledge
 - 2.2. Conditional knowledge
 - 2.3. Procedural knowledge
3. What is the metacognitive regulation of Grade 8 students of Rizal High School in Basic Mathematics in the following aspects:
 - 3.1. Prediction
 - 3.2. Planning
 - 3.3. Evaluation
 - 3.4. Monitoring
4. Are there significant relationships among the respondents' declarative knowledge, conditional knowledge, procedural knowledge and academic performance?
5. Are there significant relationships among the respondents' planning, prediction, evaluation, monitoring and academic performance?
6. Is there a linear combination of metacognitive knowledge and regulation that could adequately explain the academic performance of students in Mathematics 8?

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There are no significant relationships among the respondents' declarative knowledge, conditional knowledge, procedural knowledge and academic performance.

2. There are no significant relationships among the respondents' planning, prediction, evaluation, monitoring and academic performance.
3. There is no linear combination on the relevant variables that significantly and adequately explain or predict the classification of the respondents in terms of their level of academic performances in Mathematics 8.

Scope and Limitations

The study is conducted at the Rizal High School, Division of Pasig City. The participants are one hundred twenty (120) selected Grade 8 students from the first ten (10) Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum (EBEC) sections, S.Y. 2020-2021. This study is limited to the assessment of the metacognitive knowledge and regulation of the students towards their Basic Mathematics problem-solving performance using constructed measures based on Metacognitive Skills and Knowledge Assessment by Carlo Magno (2010).

There is a need to assess the strands of metacognition of grade 8 students by a more direct and domain-specific measure of metacognition to accurately assess the metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive regulation of the selected grade 8 students specifically with concentration on the topic regarding basic mathematical word problem.

Rather than revolving on other aspects related to metacognition, this study limited itself to the assessment of the two main components of metacognition namely the metacognitive knowledge (declarative, conditional, procedural) and metacognitive regulation of thought processes (prediction, planning, monitoring, evaluation) manifested during the word problem-solving test measure as well as the discriminatory power of the strands of metacognition in high and low performing groups.

Research Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the descriptive type of research was employed. The primary concern of this present study is to describe the nature of a situation as it exists at the time of the study and to explore the causes of a particular, phenomenon, hence, the design was utilized.

More specifically, among the several types of descriptive research, descriptive survey and descriptive analysis were chosen to fit in this study. The descriptive survey is best whenever the object of any class varies among themselves, and one is interested in knowing the extent of different conditions obtained from these objects. This typically employs questionnaires which serve the purpose of describing conditions, opinions, attitudes, perceptions of a group of people, variety of subject taken from representative or samples for the purpose of inferring the properties to the population.

The data from descriptive survey will be used as basis for inferences that may aid in solving practical problems which are of value to the researchers rather than the principles and laws applied in conducting an experiment in laboratory. The descriptive analysis was the main procedure employed in the study. This method aims to generate quantitative data to describe the similarities and differences among set products.

Research Instrument

Questionnaire through Google Forms were administered as the gathering instrument. The questionnaire includes the examinee's information, and a 5-item mathematical word-problem solving test consisting of a self-report inventory on each problem, as a measure of metacognitive ability. Standardized scoring rubrics were also utilized in the analysis and interpretation of data in each metacognitive domain. The focus of the given mathematical word problems is on Basic Mathematics.

Instrument Construction Procedure

Content Domain. The model is made up of two components: knowledge of cognition and regulation of cognition. In the knowledge of cognition component, there were sub processes that include declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge, and conditional knowledge. Prediction, planning, evaluation, and monitoring were all covered in the regulation component.

Item Writing. There were thirty-five items that were modified to measure each domain of metacognition in the context of basic mathematical problem solving. A 5-item basic mathematical word-problem solving consisting of a 7-item self-report inventory on each problem were constructed. Master teachers in Mathematics were consulted regarding the appropriateness of the problems. There was one item for each metacognitive domain (declarative, conditional, procedural, prediction, planning, evaluating and monitoring).

Sampling

There are 120 respondents to be randomly selected, 12 students from each ten (10) grade 8 Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum (EBEC) sections currently enrolled in Rizal High School, S.Y. 2020-2021 and were asked to participate in the study, all possessing the same content and competencies in Mathematics.

Data Collection and Analysis

120 respondents who were selected through equal allocation stratified random sampling technique was asked to solve the basic Mathematics problems; the problems were presented to the students through Google Forms. After the researchers were able to generate the results of the constructed measures, standardized scoring rubrics were used to analyze and interpret each of the metacognitive domains aforementioned. The researchers underwent several processes to gather data pertinent to the study. The procedural approaches are enumerated as follows:

1. **Sample Selection.** One hundred twenty (120) respondents were selected from the first ten (10) sections of the Grade 8 Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum of Rizal High School, S.Y. 2020-2021 through equal allocation stratified random sampling.
2. **Administration of Word Problem-Solving Test and Self-Report Inventory.** The researchers administered basic mathematical word problem solving test consisting of a constructed self-report inventory.
3. **Assessment of the Data.** The researchers assessed and interpreted the obtained data provided by the respondents through standardized scoring rubrics on each of the metacognitive domains.

Scaling and Scoring Technique. The semantic differential scale was used to assess whether the problem-solving task was easy or difficult on a continuum for the first item on declarative knowledge. For the conditional knowledge item, the rating on the difficulty is justified in a 5-point scale rubric.

Table 1
Rubric for item on conditional knowledge

Points	Description of Response
0	If no answer or cannot explain the difficulty given.
1	If the answer does not adequately justify the difficulty given.
2	If the answer can be accepted but does not adequately support the rating on the difficulty given.
3	If the answer partially justified the difficulty given.
4	If the answer adequately justifies the difficulty given.

For the prediction in item 3, the participants will assess if they can solve the problems correctly given 4 options in relation to their correct answer to the problem.

Table 2
Point system for the item on prediction

Item	Point System
"I am absolutely sure that I have solved the problem correctly."	With correct answer 4 points; with wrong answer 1 point
"I am sure that I have solved the problem correctly."	With correct answer 3 points; with wrong answer 2 points
"I am sure that I have not solved the problem correctly."	With correct answer give 2 points; with wrong answer 3 points
"I am absolutely sure that I have not solved the problem correctly."	With correct answer give 1 point; with wrong answer 4 points

For the planning in item 4, the participant would place the correct order on how to proceed with the problem solving given five steps. The score will depend on how he labels the five step procedures. For the procedural knowledge in item 5, the participant is tasked to enumerate the steps for the problem solving. Corresponding points are given for each relevant problem-solving step provided.

Table 3
Point system for the item on procedure

Points	Description of Response
0	If there is no solution and without answer.
1	If there is a solution but without answer.
2	If there is a solution with wrong procedure and wrong answer.
3	If there is a solution with wrong procedure and correct answer.
4	If there is a solution with correct procedure and wrong answer.
5	If there is a solution with correct procedure and correct answer.

For the evaluation on item 6, the participant will select how sure he is in his answer given with four options.

Table 4
Point system for evaluation

Item	Point System
"I am absolutely sure that I have solved the problem correctly."	With correct answer 4 points; with wrong answer 1 point
"I am sure that I have solved the problem correctly."	With correct answer 3 points; with wrong answer 2 points
"I am sure that I have not solved the problem correctly."	With correct answer give 2 points; with wrong answer 3 points
"I am absolutely sure that I have not solved the problem correctly."	With correct answer give 1 point; with wrong answer 4 points

Item 7 measures monitoring. There are four options, and the participant will respond to each given four-point scale from most important to not important at all. Four-points is given for the correct sequence of it.

Item Review. The procedure and items of the measure were checked and reviewed by Master Teachers in the field. During the process, the conceptual definition for each domain was provided, as well as a table of specifications indicating the scaling technique and item description. The experts reviewed the appropriateness of the items based on the conceptual definition. Necessary changes were made after the assessment tool was revised.

Mathematical Achievement/Academic Performance. To interpret the qualitative description of the average of the first and second quarter ratings of the respondents in Mathematics 8, the table below was used:

Table 5
Interpretation for mathematical achievement / academic performance

Range	Qualitative Description
90 and above	Advanced (A)
85-89	Proficient (P)
80-84	Approaching Proficiency (AP)
75-79	Developing (D)
74 and below	Beginning (B)

Metacognitive Knowledge and Awareness. To interpret the level of metacognitive knowledge and regulation, succeeding tables were used in the results and discussion.

Statistical Tools

1. **Mean.** This was used in getting the average score of the students on each of the seven components of the two domains of metacognition which are the metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive regulation as well as the average of the academic performance of the grade 8 students during the first and second quarter in Mathematics 8, S.Y. 2020-2021.

2. **Pearson R.** This was utilized to determine if there is a significant relationship of the levels of academic performance and the levels of metacognitive knowledge and the relationship between the levels of academic performance and levels of metacognitive regulation.

3. **Multiple Discriminant Analysis.** This was utilized to determine the variables that have the great discriminatory power in predicting high and low performers.

Results and Discussion

Academic Performance of the Respondents

Table 6

Academic performance of the Grade 8 respondents in Mathematics

Level	Frequency	Percent
Advanced	27	22.5
Proficient	39	32.5
Approaching Proficiency	30	25.0
Developing	16	13.3
Beginning	8	6.7
Total	120	100.0
Mean Grade	84.74	
QD	Approaching Proficiency	

The table shows that there were 120 respondents: 6.7% of them belonged to beginning level performance; 13.3% of the respondents belonged to developing students; 25.0% belonged to approaching proficiency level; most of respondents belonged to those proficient level with percentage of 32.5%; 22.5% of them belong to advanced level in Mathematics. Overall, the respondents of the study were on the stage of approaching proficiency in mathematics with 84.74 as mean grade. The mean grade suggests that the achievement level of the respondents in Mathematics is not that high.

The Metacognitive Knowledge of Grade 8 Rizal High School Students in Basic Mathematics

Table 7

Mean rating of respondents in declarative knowledge

Problem	Mean	Qualitative Description
Problem 1	8.29	Very Easy
Problem 2	6.26	Moderately Easy
Problem 3	6.98	Moderately Easy
Problem 4	5.73	Moderately Easy
Problem 5	5.39	Moderately Easy
Overall	6.53	Moderately Easy

Legend: 7.50-10.00: Very Easy; 5.00-7.49: Moderately Easy; 2.50-4.99: Moderately Difficult; 1.00-2.49: Very Difficult

The descriptive statistics of metacognition based on declarative knowledge of the respondents is exemplified in table 7. Analysis shows that the respondents' perception towards the five basic mathematical problems was moderately easy with a general mean of 6.53. Frequently then, even before actually solving each of the indicated problems, the respondents would think somehow they could solve the given problems.

Thus, they recognized their capacity of performing the solutions and eventually arriving at the right answers by having the idea of what solving procedure would they apply to answer the given problems. The difficulty of the problems falls on the extent to which their memory can still afford to retrieve needed information to do the solving process consequently affecting their performance.

Moreover, Problem 1 which is about sets was the easiest of the five problems given and problem 5 was the most difficult for them which is about fraction. This supports the claim of Valdez (2014) that students have difficulty in solving problems involving fractions.

Table 8

Frequency distribution of respondents' declarative knowledge

Level	Frequency	Percent
Very Easy	39	32.5
Moderately Easy	55	45.8
Moderately Difficult	25	20.8
Very Difficult	1	0.8
Total	120	100.0

Table 8 shows the descriptive statistics of metacognition based on frequency distribution of respondents' declarative knowledge. The table also shows that 32.5% of the respondents perceived that the given problems were very easy, 45.8% moderately easy, 20.8% moderately difficult and only 0.8% of them perceived the problems as very difficult. This further means that respondents' perception on the difficulty level of basic concepts on mathematics was not that difficult because greater number of them perceived mathematical word problems as very easy and moderately easy. However, it refutes Laguna (2013) claims that most students consider mathematics as extremely difficult, tedious and mind numbing and the claim of Valdez (2014) that students are stereotyping that Mathematics is a difficult subject.

Table 9

Mean rating of respondents' conditional knowledge

Problem	Mean	Qualitative Description
Problem 1	2.63	Very Satisfactory
Problem 2	2.10	Satisfactory
Problem 3	2.11	Satisfactory
Problem 4	2.04	Satisfactory
Problem 5	1.79	Satisfactory
Overall	2.13	Satisfactory

Legend: 3.20-4.00: Outstanding; 2.40-3.19: Very Satisfactory; 1.60-2.39: Satisfactory; 0.80-1.59: Poor; 0.00-0.79: Very Poor

Table 9 shows the descriptive statistics of metacognition based on conditional knowledge of the respondents. The result shows that the respondents manifested a satisfactory level of knowledge about when and why to use their acquired learning procedures in solving each of the five mathematical problems which is indicated in the generated general mean of 2.13.

This highlights the idea that most of the respondents somewhat know why such solving procedure conceived upon their first reading of each of the problem be used to satisfy what is being asked. Furthermore, the respondents had a very satisfactory rating in justifying the difficulty given in problem 1 and satisfactory rating in problems 2-5.

Table 10
Frequency distribution of respondents' conditional knowledge

Level	Frequency	Percent
Outstanding	15	12.5
Very Satisfactory	34	28.3
Satisfactory	43	35.8
Poor	21	17.5
Very Poor	7	5.8
Total	120	100.0

Table 10 shows the frequency distribution of respondents conditional knowledge. The table presents that 12.5% of the respondents were outstanding in justifying the difficulty given in 5 problems, 28.3% with very satisfactory rating, the respondents were predominant with satisfactory rating that justifies the aforementioned statement, 17.5% poor rating and 5.8% with very poor justification.

With close scrutiny on some individual responses, some of the respondents could not justify why they give such difficulty rating this is supported by the presence of students with very poor and poor rating on their conditional knowledge. Some were still indeterminate of what particular strategy they are going to use and if that strategy suits the given problem.

Table 11
Mean rating of respondents' procedural knowledge

Problem	Mean	Qualitative Description
Problem 1	2.08	Fairly Satisfactory
Problem 2	2.59	Satisfactory
Problem 3	1.62	Poor
Problem 4	1.50	Poor
Problem 5	2.05	Fairly Satisfactory
Overall	1.97	Fairly Satisfactory

Legend: 4.15-5.00: Outstanding; 3.32-4.14: Very Satisfactory; 2.49-3.31: Satisfactory; 1.67-2.48: Fairly Satisfactory; 0.84-1.66: Poor; 0.00-0.83: Very Poor

Table 11 shows the descriptive statistics of metacognition based on procedural knowledge of the respondents. The table shows that the respondents exhibited a fairly satisfactory level of knowledge in the procedural aspect of solving, particularly on how to implement the solving procedures or strategies to solve the given problems with a general mean of 1.97. This points out that the respondents are not so aware of what particular steps they are going to impose to gain right answers.

In addition, the respondents had poor level of knowledge in the procedural aspect in problems 3 and 4 that are all about discount and interest, fairly satisfactory in problems 1 and 5 that is about sets and fractions respectively, and a satisfactory knowledge in the procedural aspect in problem 2 that is about ratio and proportion.

Table 12
Frequency distribution of respondents' procedural knowledge

Level	Frequency	Percent
Outstanding	0	0.0
Very Satisfactory	1	0.8
Satisfactory	31	25.8
Fairly Satisfactory	42	35.0
Poor	29	24.2
Very Poor	17	14.2
Total	120	100.0

Table 12 presents the frequency distribution of respondents' procedural knowledge. This shows that there is no outstanding procedural knowledge, 0.8% very satisfactory, 25.8% satisfactory, 35.0% fairly satisfactory, 24.2% poor, and 14.2% of them has a very poor procedural knowledge.

On the contrary, the above statements of the respondents who performed correct procedures in solving for what is asked in the problem arrived at a wrong answer because they encountered mistakes as regards basic mathematical operations such as addition and division and understanding what is being asked. Furthermore, the respondents rate the problems as moderately easy but find difficulty in solving them.

For that reason, problems on basic mathematical operations are again on the limelight of the study. This substantiates that there are students who still faced problems on accuracy and understanding towards mathematical word problems. Students were not capable of solving mathematical word problems correctly if they were not able to master both the pre-requisite knowledge and the skill on operations. The findings support the claim of Laguna (2013) that students have not yet mastered the pre-requisite knowledge and skills in solving the aforementioned topics.

Metacognitive Regulation of the Respondents in Basic Mathematics

Table 13
Frequency distribution of respondents' predicting

Level	Frequency	Percent
Outstanding	5	4.2
Very Satisfactory	22	18.3
Satisfactory	41	34.2
Poor	43	35.8
Very Poor	9	7.5
Total	120	100.0

The descriptive statistics of metacognition based on prediction of the respondents is shown in Table 13. It can be gleaned from the table that 4.2% of the respondents made an outstanding prediction in the five problems, 18.3% of them have very satisfactory prediction, 34.2 % of the respondents with satisfactory prediction on the 5 problems, 35.8% with poor prediction level and 7.5% of them with very poor prediction.

Furthermore, based on the individual inventory of the respondents, there was a larger scale of those who predicted that they could solve the problems correctly and eventually arrive at a wrong answer compared to those who predicted that they could not solve the problems correctly and eventually got wrong answers. Hence, students perceived the problems as moderately easy and predicted that they can solve the problem, but they tend not to predict their own skill.

Thus, students who are indulged in solving mathematical word problems are less likely aware that they cannot solve a given problem. This reveals that when students were asked to solve mathematical word problems they already had an optimistic impression towards such especially if they can recall the concept; they would immediately give an assurance that they could get the right answer. This reveals that many are no longer affected by stereotypes with regard Mathematics as a subject that refutes the claim of Valdez (2014) that students are stereotyping that mathematics is a difficult subject. The difference on the findings can be attributed perhaps to the time that the studies conducted that is the teachers already find ways in reducing stereotyping on the part of the student in the recent study.

Table 14
Mean rating of the respondents' planning

Problem	Mean	Qualitative Description
Problem 1	2.56	Poor
Problem 2	2.36	Poor
Problem 3	2.34	Poor
Problem 4	2.35	Poor
Problem 5	2.27	Poor
Overall	2.38	Poor

Legend: 4.20-5.00: Outstanding; 3.40-4.19: Very Satisfactory; 2.60-3.39: Satisfactory; 1.80-2.59: Poor; 1.00-1.79: Very Poor

Table 14 shows the descriptive statistics of metacognition based on planning of the respondents. Analysis shows that the respondents demonstrate poor level of planning procedure towards all of the problems with a mean of 2.38. This denotes that the planning procedure utilized by most of the respondents involves inappropriate selection of strategies and allocation of knowledge and time resources that have eventually affect their performance.

In addition to the mean rating of respondents' planning is their planning's frequency distribution situated on table 15. The table shows 5% of the respondents had outstanding planning, 3.3% had very satisfactory planning, 33.3% had satisfactory planning, and 41.7 and 16.7% had poor and very poor planning. The respondents find difficulty solving the problems because most of them could not devise an appropriate plan.

Table 15
Frequency distribution of the respondents' planning

Level	Frequency	Percent
Outstanding	6	5.0
Very Satisfactory	4	3.3
Satisfactory	40	33.3
Poor	50	41.7
Very Poor	20	16.7
Total	120	100.0

The sample responses on the individual inventory of the respondents consequently justify the result of the analysis. This means that prior to actual solving, most of the respondents were not able to cognize the different solving procedures they would employ to solve each of the problem.

Furthermore, there was no systematic and adequate act of planning on the part of students and neglected perhaps the importance of planning in arriving with the correct answer with regard to Mathematics. Thus, students are being reinforced to envision clear and appropriate method of gaining correct solutions and answers to mathematical word problems.

Table 16
Frequency distribution of the respondents' evaluation

Level	Frequency	Percent
Outstanding	6	5.0
Very Satisfactory	19	15.8
Satisfactory	48	40.0
Poor	40	33.3
Very Poor	7	5.8
Total	120	100.0

Table 16 shows the descriptive statistics of metacognition based on evaluation of the respondents. The result exemplifies that 5% of the respondents made an outstanding evaluation in the five problems, 15.8% of them had very satisfactory evaluation, 40.0% of the respondents with satisfactory evaluation, 33.3% with poor evaluation, and 5.8% of them with very poor evaluation.

This means that majority of the respondents had better evaluation than prediction and are rest assured that they have poor performance in solving the given problems and evaluated their strategies used as not that perfectly suited and sufficient to obtain what is being demanded in each problem.

As indicated in the quantitative analysis and results of the self-inventory, larger scale of the respondents guaranteed their wrong answers to the problems after the solving process. These points out that there is a change in mind manifested from before and after answering the problems. Through such the students were able to evaluate themselves whether they had mastered the mathematical concepts or not.

Hence, this emphasizes that even Grade 8 students are deemed poor in mastery of skills and concepts as regards basic Mathematics. This supports the claim of Valdez (2014) that students' evaluation was not that good.

Table 17
Mean rating of respondents' monitoring

Problem	Mean	Qualitative Description
Problem 1	1.21	Poor
Problem 2	1.18	Poor
Problem 3	1.16	Poor
Problem 4	1.04	Poor
Problem 5	1.09	Poor
Overall	1.14	Poor

Legend: 3.20-4.00: Outstanding; 2.40-3.19: Very Satisfactory; 1.60-2.39: Satisfactory; 0.80-1.59: Poor; 0.00-0.79: Very Poor

Table 17 shows that the respondents demonstrated poor monitoring performance towards determining the levels of importance of indicated steps to be considered in order to succeed in a problem solving as based on their own perception towards mathematical problem-solving procedures given by the mean of 1.14. This also means that the respondents had a relatively low degree of assessment on their learning or strategy used. They were not able to monitor their own on-line awareness of comprehension and task performance.

Table 18
Frequency distribution of respondents' monitoring

Level	Frequency	Percent
Outstanding	14	11.7
Very Satisfactory	0	0
Satisfactory	18	15.0
Poor	42	35.0
Very Poor	46	38.3
Total	120	100.0

Table 18 shows that 11.7% of the respondents had outstanding monitoring level, 15% had satisfactory level and dominated by the respondents with poor and very poor monitoring level that composed of 35% and 38.3% respectively. The result indicates that the respondents were really not aware about the degree to which the presented steps vary according to their importance, which can be considered as predictors of success in a problem-solving activity when done accordingly.

Consequently, students' knowledge on how to take into consideration each of the diverse steps on solving mathematical word problems can help them organize their approach in acquiring correct answers towards the said problems. This refutes Cardona (2017) who claims that students had satisfactory monitoring level.

Table 19
Comparison between the academic performance of the respondents in Mathematics, declarative knowledge, conditional knowledge and procedural knowledge

	Pearson r	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Interpretation
Academic Performance and Declarative Knowledge	0.185	0.043	0.043 < 0.05	Reject	Significant
Academic Performance and Conditional Knowledge	0.419	0.000	0.000 < 0.05	Reject	Significant
Academic Performance and Procedural Knowledge	0.226	0.013	0.013 < 0.05	Reject	Significant
Declarative Knowledge and Conditional Knowledge	0.250	0.006	0.006 < 0.05	Reject	Significant
Declarative Knowledge and Procedural Knowledge	0.297	0.001	0.001 < 0.05	Reject	Significant
Conditional Knowledge and Procedural Knowledge	0.341	0.000	0.000 < 0.05	Reject	Significant

Pearson r table is constructed to show the correlation between the aspects of metacognitive knowledge and academic performance of the respondents. Table 19 shows that the variables Academic Performance, Declarative Knowledge, Conditional Knowledge, and Procedural Knowledge are significantly related to each other. A p-value of 0.043, less than 0.05 that shows a significant relationship between academic performance and declarative knowledge of students. This means that if a student has higher academic performance then his perception to a given problem is easier. Significant relationship with positive correlation for the academic performance and conditional knowledge is also brought by the Pearson r value of 0.419 and a p-value of 0.000, less than 0.05. Thus, students with higher academic performance can give better justifications about their perceived rating of difficulty. Significant relationship with positive correlation is also true for the academic performance and procedural knowledge is also brought by the Pearson r value of 0.229 and a p-value of 0.013, less than 0.05. Thus, students with higher academic performance have a higher procedural.

The intercorrelation between the aspects of metacognitive knowledge shows positive significant correlation too. Declarative knowledge and conditional knowledge have a computed Pearson r value of 0.250 and p-value of 0.006 less than 0.05, declarative and procedural knowledge with Pearson r value equal to 0.297 and p-value of 0.001, and declarative knowledge and procedural knowledge with a positive Pearson r value of 0.341 and a less than 0.05 p-value. These findings show that, having a higher academic performance in mathematics could be possible by enhancing the aspects of metacognitive knowledge of the students. This shows that declarative knowledge and conditional knowledge are consistent with the other measures and this result is consistent with other studies. Also, this presents the idea that the overall metacognitive process increases when a learner uses his declarative and conditional knowledge.

These findings indicate that the use of one's knowledge of intellectual resources and the need to learn information greatly comprises an increment on metacognitive abilities and contribute to higher mathematics performance. This supports the findings of Magno (2009) on his study on the metacognitive knowledge correlation which showed positive significant relationships.

Table 20
Relationship between the academic performance of the respondents in Mathematics, prediction, planning, evaluation, and monitoring

	Pearson r	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Interpretation
Academic Performance and Prediction	-0.039	0.675	0.675 > 0.05	Accept	Not Significant
Academic Performance and Planning	0.404	0.000	0.000 < 0.05	Reject	Significant
Academic Performance and Evaluating	0.041	0.655	0.655 > 0.05	Accept	Not Significant
Declarative Knowledge and Monitoring	0.101	0.275	0.275 > 0.05	Accept	Not Significant
Prediction and Planning	0.085	0.356	0.356 > 0.05	Accept	Not Significant
Prediction and Evaluating	0.790	0.000	0.000 < 0.05	Reject	Significant
Prediction and Monitoring	-0.115	0.211	0.211 > 0.05	Accept	Not Significant
Planning and Evaluating	0.014	0.880	0.880 > 0.05	Accept	Not Significant
Planning and Monitoring	0.086	0.349	0.349 > 0.05	Accept	Not Significant
Evaluating and Monitoring	-0.004	0.962	0.962 > 0.05	Accept	Not Significant

Table 21
Standardized canonical discriminant function coefficients

	Declarative knowledge	Conditional knowledge	Planning	Prediction	Procedural knowledge	Evaluation	Monitoring	Monitoring
Canonical Discriminant Coefficients	.230	.102	-.446	.457	-.374	.625	-.364	-.18
Wilk's Lambda	.996	1.00	.977	.863	.960	.859	.988	1.00
Eigen value	.735	.361						
Canonical Correlation	.515							

Thus, the grade 8 students were really conscious on their process of forecasting their possible performances whether they can or cannot solve a given mathematical task correctly and estimating their performances whether they have or have not solved the given mathematical task properly although they were more accurate in forecasting their performance during the evaluation which was after solving the word problems compared to their prediction which was done before solving the word problems.

Table 20 is generated to determine the significant correlation between the aspects of metacognitive regulation and academic performance of the respondents. Table 20 shows two positive significant correlation. First, the academic performance of the respondents is significantly correlated with their planning. This means that when a students have a high mathematics performance he can have a higher level of planning and when a students have a high level of planning they can have a higher mathematical performance.

But when a student has low mathematics performance it leads to lower planning level and when a student has a low level of planning it leads to lower mathematics performance. Secondly, prediction and evaluation are also significantly correlated. This further means that if a student can predict the possible outcome correctly without solving then he might evaluate his answer after solving correctly but if a student cannot predict the possible outcome correctly without solving then he might not evaluate his answer correctly after solving. Prediction and evaluation would tell whether a person is aware about ones skills or not.

Using Multiple Discriminant Analysis, the table shows the generated canonical correlation which is 0.515 shows a moderate relation of the discriminant scores and the group low and high performing group. Furthermore, the eigen value is 0.36 which shows the efficacy of the determinant function. The table also shows the Wilk's Lambda of 0.74 that implies a high discriminative power in determining low performing and high performing grade 8 students. In addition, the table imposed that prediction and evaluation were most predictive, hence most powerful in discriminating between low performing and high performing grade 8 students. It is indicated by the two largest canonical discriminant coefficients which are 0.46 and 0.63 respectively. These imply that those with great prediction and evaluation were most likely to have a high metacognitive awareness.

Table 22
Classification results

		Grade in Mathematics 8	Predicted Group Membership		Total
			Low	High	
Original	Count	Low	52	2	54
		High	16	50	66
		Ungrouped cases	0	0	0
%		1.00	96.3	3.7	100.0
		2.00	24.2	75.8	100.0
		Ungrouped cases	100.0	.0	100.0

Only the cases in the analysis are subjected to cross validation. In the cross validation, each case is classified using functions derived from all cases other than that case. 85% of the cases in the original groups were correctly classified.

The classification table shows that the eight components of metacognition have linear combination with (and not independently of) each other and could correctly classify or distinguish or predict the performance of 85% of the respondents. The eight-variable discriminant was relatively better in predicting low performing grade 8 students than high performing. In fact, the discriminant function could correctly predict 96% of those who are low performing grade 8 students and 76% of those who are high performing grade 8 students. In other words, the multivariate discriminant function could correctly predict five (5) out of every five (5) low performing grade 8 students and about three (3) out of every five (5) high performing grade 8 students. Overall, the discriminant function can correctly predict the performance of eight (8) out of 10 grade 8 students.

Hence, if one knows whether a student has a high declarative knowledge or low, whether s/he can justify the difficulty given to such mathematical word problem or not, whether s/he can correctly predict if s/he can solve the problem well or not, whether s/he has a correct plan in solving a mathematical word problem or not, whether s/he has a correct procedure in solving or not, whether s/he can correctly evaluate her/his answer or not and s/he can monitor his/her work properly, then one can correctly predict with 85% probability whether the student is low or high performing student.

This means that the eight pieces of information can adequately predict or discriminate between those low or high performing grade 8 students specifically Prediction and Evaluation. Therefore, there is a linear combination of the academic performance and other relevant variables that can significantly and adequately explain or predict the classification of the respondents in terms of their levels of performance on mathematical task.

Summary of Findings

A. Academic Performance of Grade 8 Students

The overall Academic Performance in Mathematics of selected Grade 8 Rizal High School students in mathematical word problem solving is of Approaching Proficiency with a computed mean grade of 84.7367, a mean grade that was very close to 85 that denotes a proficient level.

Moreover, academic performance also has a significant positive correlation with the aspects of metacognitive knowledge namely: declarative knowledge, conditional knowledge and procedural knowledge and their planning, this is showed by the computed p-value of 0.043, 0.000, 0.013, and .000 respectively.

B. Metacognitive Knowledge of Selected Grade 8 Rizal High School Students

B.1 Declarative Knowledge

The overall rating of declarative knowledge of the Grade 8 Rizal High School students in mathematical word problem solving was moderately easy with the computed mean of 6.53.

Declarative knowledge also has a significant correlation with the other aspects of metacognitive knowledge and academic performance.

B.2 Conditional Knowledge

The selected Grade 8 Rizal High School students had a satisfactory conditional knowledge with the computed mean of 2.13. This implies that students can justify the difficulty given to such mathematical word problem. Furthermore, students can provide a sufficient explanation why they give such rating of difficulty to mathematical word problems in the same compartment. Conditional knowledge also has a significant correlation with the other aspects of metacognitive knowledge and academic performance.

B.3 Procedural Knowledge

Generally, the selected Grade 8 Rizal High School Students had a fairly satisfactory procedural knowledge with the computed mean of 1.97. This shows that they have a fairly satisfactory process in solving a mathematical word problem. Furthermore, procedural knowledge also has a significant correlation with the other aspects of metacognitive knowledge and academic performance.

C. Metacognitive Regulation of Selected Grade 8 Rizal High School Students

C.1 Prediction

Most of the Grade 8 Rizal High School students had a poor prediction level which was 35.8% of the total number of respondents. Most of the respondents also professed they can solve the mathematical task but are cynic with the resulting answer. Prediction and evaluation were also significantly correlated but not with other aspects of metacognitive regulation and academic performance. This further means that if a student can predict the possible outcome correctly without solving then he might evaluate his answer after solving correctly but if a student cannot predict the possible outcome correctly without solving then he might not evaluate his answer after solving correctly.

C.2 Planning

The overall level of the Grade 8 Rizal High School students' planning is poor with a mean of 2.38. This shows that they have a poor plan on how they will attack or solve the given mathematical task. Planning has a significant relationship with the academic performance but no significant relationship with other aspects of metacognitive regulation.

C.3 Evaluation

The imperative results about how the Grade 8 Rizal High School students conduct an evaluation about their solutions or answers shows that 5% of the respondents made an outstanding evaluation in the five problems, 15.8% of them had very satisfactory evaluation, 40.0% of the respondents with satisfactory evaluation, 3.33% with poor evaluation, and 5.8% of them with very poor evaluation. Prediction and evaluation are also significantly correlated but not with other aspects of metacognitive regulation and academic performance. This further means that if a student can predict the possible outcome correctly without solving then he might evaluate his answer after solving correctly but if a student cannot predict the possible outcome correctly without solving then he might not evaluate his answer after solving correctly.

C.4 Monitoring

The important findings about how the Grade 8 Rizal High School Students demonstrate poor monitoring performance towards determining the levels of importance of indicated steps to be considered in order to succeed in a problem solving as based on their own perception towards mathematical problem-solving procedures was given by the mean of 1.14. This also means that the respondents have a relatively low degree of assessment to their learning or strategy used. They were not able to monitor their own on-line awareness of comprehension and task performance. The result entails that the respondents are really not aware about the degree to which the presented steps vary according to their importance, which can be considered as predictors of success in a problem-solving activity when done accordingly. Moreover, no significant relationship of monitoring and the other aspects of metacognitive regulation and academic performance were found.

D. Respondents and the Subdivisions of the Two Domains of Metacognition

There was a significant relationship in the academic performance of selected Grade 8 Rizal High School Students and the aspects of metacognitive knowledge as brought by the generated intercorrelation data. There was also a significant relationship in the academic performance of Grade 8 Rizal High School Students and the way they plan and strategies in solving basic mathematical word problems and the way they make prediction and evaluation regarding their performance.

Conclusions

The academic performance in Basic Mathematics of the respondents needs bold improvement. The basic mathematical word problems are moderately easy, but most Grade 8 students have difficulty solving the problem. Even though respondents portrayed relatively high level of declarative and conditional knowledge, it tends to decrease as they proceed to the component procedural knowledge. The respondents are impulsive, or they found difficulties in problem solving by simply implementing action taught by the teacher without considering appropriate interventions uniquely attached to each of the word problems.

Although Grade 8 Rizal High School Students demonstrated poor level of planning and monitoring, that shows to be a weak indication that it was transformed to a great deal of confidence when predicting or evaluating that they are sure that they arrived to a correct answer. Students' academic performance has a positive relationship with the aspects of metacognitive knowledge and planning, this could be a ground to enhance these aspects to increase academic performance in mathematics.

The level of prediction and evaluation of grade 8 students towards basic mathematical word problems can adequately discriminate the level of performance in basic mathematics. Low achievers are better classified than the high achievers though. There is a linear combination in the components of metacognitive knowledge and regulation that can significantly and adequately explain or predict the classification of the respondents in terms of their levels of academic performance on any mathematical task.

Recommendations

1. Improve mastery of concepts in basic mathematics especially in basic secondary education. It is encouraged then that other than the habit of compassionate teaching, the mathematics department must rigorously implement programmed remedial and intervention classes to low math ability groups and programmed advanced classes to high math ability groups. Moreover, both the teachers and students should monitor the students' progress on a daily basis.
2. Instill on the minds of teachers that process is equally important as the answer in solving mathematical word problems. This can be aided by using holistic or analytical rubric in the scoring technique.
3. Immerse the students with varied, multidisciplinary, non-routine and localized problems in basic mathematics so that with the aid of high level of planning and monitoring, students especially those who belong to low math ability groups will be led to attaining accurate prediction and evaluation of their performance in the problem-solving process.
4. Stereotyping that Mathematics is difficult must be continuously acted upon so that the persistence to love basic mathematics be redirected to a higher ground. This can be done by providing teachers with concrete, more meaningful, and firsthand experiences to word problems involving the concepts of Basic Mathematics. However, the knowledge of solving problems must also receive a big emphasis.
5. Planning, strategy making, and monitoring skills of students must be enhanced to improve their performance in Mathematics so that students great deal of confidence in saying that they are sure that they arrived with a correct answer would be greater.
6. Grade 8 Rizal High School Students must elicit in themselves the will to love mathematics and undergo the whole process of mathematical word problem solving so that they will be effective movers in whatever profession they'll play in the society in the near future.
7. Focusing on the enhancement of the aspects of metacognition and the factors affecting them would be of great help to elevate mathematical performance of students.
8. Spiral Progression Approach in Mathematics should be strengthened through Metacognitive Approach in teaching to effectively achieve its goal of delivering seamless progression in learning Mathematics.
9. Empower teachers' teaching strategies in line with metacognition for them to better help students manage and evaluate their own learning.
10. Replicate the study especially in the basic education so that an early treatment can be devised in their level.

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